

Start on Sustainability Starter Kit

4. SERVING GREEN CONSUMERS

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ABOUT OUR PROJECT

By implementing Start on Sustainability, we aim **to equip micro-enterprises** with the necessary **tools and resources** to take meaningful action towards sustainability, thereby contributing to a more sustainable and resilient EU economy.

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**SERVING GREEN
CONSUMERS**

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OVERVIEW OF THE TOPIC

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LEARNING OUTCOMES

INTRODUCTION TO SERVING GREEN CONSUMERS

- Pollution is a widespread issue and a significant threat to people, especially in urban areas, due to rapid industrialization and geometric growth rates.
- Most businesses and consumers around the world face the challenge of conserving resources and protecting the environment, as consumer behaviour is the root cause of many environmental issues.

INTRODUCTION TO SERVING GREEN CONSUMERS

- As consumers become more conscious of what they purchase and interested in how their consumption patterns affect the environment, young consumers are aware of eco-friendly purchase options. Thus the adoption of green habits influences their consumption habits.
- A better understanding of the eco-friendliness of product use and disposal can help identify opportunities to reduce environmental impacts.

GREEN CONSUMPTION

- In recent decades, there has been a substantial shift in consumer behaviour, with environmental and health awareness playing a major influence.
- Green consumption behaviour involves using sustainable, eco-friendly products and avoiding the ones that are harmful for both the consumers and the environment.

GREEN CONSUMPTION

Green consumption is typically associated with environmentally responsible consumption, in which consumers consider the environmental impact of a) purchasing, using, and b) disposing of various products or using various green services.

- While purchasing, the focus is on personal gain
- While disposing, it benefits the environment, society, and others.

It involves acting with social responsibility and social consciousness, using environmentally friendly products, selecting recyclable products with high durability, quality, and ecological labelling, avoiding excessive consumption, and decreasing resource and energy usage.

GREEN PRODUCTS

- Environment friendly products use recyclable materials, reduce waste and energy usage, reduce packaging, and use fewer toxic ingredients that have the least negative impact on the environment during production and consumption.

GREEN PRODUCTS

- They have a green life cycle and can have a more positive impact on the environment than other products that do not reduce negative impacts.
- Adopting green goods improves health, increases recycling, and diminishes environmental harm.
- Customers also earn economic gains due to these benefits, such as decreased environmental expenses and company waste disposal costs.

GREEN CONSUMERISM

- Green consumerism refers to customers using environmentally friendly products but with different focuses and meanings.
- It involves buying environmentally friendly products and avoiding products that are harmful to the environment, minimising the use of natural resources and hazardous substances, and demonstrating responsibility for environmental protection.

GREEN CONSUMERISM

- Green consumption encompasses not only the purchase and use of environmentally friendly products, but also the decision by consumers' decision to buy recycled products.
- The global environmental crisis has led to a surge in demand for eco-friendly alternatives.
- Consumers are becoming more educated and savvy, demanding more transparent and strategic green initiatives.
- They demand more responsibility and action from businesses and sustainability.

GREEN CONSUMERISM

- Green consumerism has changed the way businesses approach marketing and customer engagement. Also the urgency to address climate change, conserve resources and reduce pollution has made eco-friendly production methods and recycling imperative. This mindset involves supporting goods and services that are environmental friendly.

GREEN CONSUMERISM

- Economic, social, and cultural factors have shaped the concept of green consumerism, which focuses on promoting awareness of companies' production practices and advocating for the use of products that are not harmful to the environment.
- This movement aims to encourage individuals to make more sustainable choices and only support businesses that prioritise eco-friendly practices.
- By aligning consumers' behaviours with organisations' profit motives, green consumerism establishes a balance between sustainability and profitability.

GREEN CONSUMERISM

- To succeed in the modern marketplace, companies must adopt a green mindset.
- Green Consumerism is a growing trend that encourages the consumption of goods and services based on environmentally friendly manufacturing principles.
- This shift is driven by the increasing awareness of environmental challenges such as rising sea levels, global temperatures, and deforestation.

GREEN CONSUMERISM

- Green consumers make choices based on the environmental credentials of products, such as ethical purchase choices, product use, and post-use, and the use of organic products made with low impact processes.
- The importance of green consumerism includes reduced waste in packaging, increased energy efficiency, decreased emissions and pollutants during production and transportation processes, and consumption of healthier, more sustainable foods.

GREEN CONSUMERISM

- The UN Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (1988), Kyoto Protocol (1997), and Paris Climate Agreement (2016) are all milestones in the path towards reducing human impact on the environment.
- The increased availability of environmental data online and on social media empowers green consumers to make environmentally conscious choices.

TARGETING GREEN CONSUMERS

- Green consumption involves consciously choosing products and services that are environmentally friendly.
- Consumers are typically driven by both social and environmental concerns, aiming to help address environmental issues and conserve natural resources.

TARGETING GREEN CONSUMERS

- Practising green living can provide personal benefits, such as avoiding harmful chemicals, reducing energy costs, and promoting overall well-being.
- Embracing green consumer behaviour involves prioritising the environment when deciding on goods, technologies, and consumption habits.

- Governments have made significant efforts in promoting a net-zero future to limit dangerous warming, but still falling short of meeting the goals of the Paris Agreement.
- This gap between ambition and action is also evident in the private sector, where more companies are committed to tackling sustainability goals.
- A significant source of untapped potential for positive impact is - the role that businesses can play in helping billions of ordinary citizens make more sustainable choices and change habits and behaviours.

- One way to address this issue is by focusing on shaping sustainable habits and choices.
- Consumer power can scale change, as many of the world's biggest consumer-facing brands and businesses were at COP26, promoting their sustainability credentials.
- Making sustainable choices easier for consumers is another strategy.
- Making sustainable choices can be difficult due to the complexity, time-consuming, or expensive nature of the process.

- Creating incentives to shape sustainable behaviours is another approach.
- Businesses can use closing the "say-do gap" as an opportunity to make sustainable choices easy, enjoyable, and affordable, accelerating change on the sustainability agenda and helping customers do things they say they want to do but cannot easily.
- This approach is an example of a company with a sustainability agenda innovating by building new habits and tapping into consumers' already inclined and motivated actions.

- Leveraging existing consumer insights and knowledge for action is another approach that does not require deep sustainability expertise across the business.
- By finding the aspirations, challenges and disappointments of their customers, companies can innovate solutions, products, and new business models, driving value and serving customers while creating a positive impact.

- Businesses can educate consumers about the benefits and impact of their products and services.
- They can also inspire consumers to make sustainable choices by creating a vision and mission that appeals to their emotions, values, and aspirations.
- By empowering consumers to make sustainable choices, businesses can create a positive impact on the world, gain a competitive advantage, and build a loyal customer base.

GREEN MARKETING

Green marketing is a business practice that promotes products and services based on environmental initiatives, aiming to encourage consumers to make more sustainable choices and create a positive impact on the environment.

GREEN MARKETING PRACTICES

- **Product development:** Creating products with minimal environmental impact, using sustainable and energy efficient materials.
- **Marketing strategies:** Advertising, product packaging, and branding that highlight environmental initiatives.
- **Supply chain management:** Optimising operations, minimising waste, and adopting sustainable practices to reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

GREEN MARKETING PRACTICES

- **Corporate social responsibility:** Building a reputation for environmental stewardship through environmentally responsible practices.
- **Consumer education:** Encouraging consumers about their environmental impact and sustainable practices.

POPULARISATION OF GREEN MARKETING

- In the 1980s and 90s, environmental marketing faced skepticism due to "greenwashing," where companies falsely claimed their products were environmentally friendly.
- This led to calls for more rigorous standards and transparency in green marketing.
- The 2000s saw the introduction of the new regulations and certifications like Energy Star, Fair Trade, and organic labels.

- Green marketing became more mainstream in the 2010s.
- Businesses recognised the value of sustainability and began incorporating it into their marketing strategies and social responsibility initiatives.
- Green marketing has evolved to incorporate sustainable business practices, including social and ethical concerns, making it an integral part of business practices.
- Global collaboration for sustainability is a key trend in the future of green business, as governments, businesses, and non-profit organisations work together to address environmental challenges.
- Streamlined communication becomes more important, with marketing automation tools and customer relationship management (CRM) tools enabling global collaboration and advancing sustainable measures.

SUSTAINABLE MARKETING

- Sustainable marketing is a strategic move to connect with conscious consumers and is here to stay, as it integrates technology, fosters global collaboration, and responds to changing customer requirements.

GREEN MARKETING STRATEGIES

- Factors influencing green consumer behaviour include satisfaction, performance, value, environmental advantages, and claims made on packaging labels.
- Financial rewards can also encourage more frequent purchases and usage of green items.
- Supports such as improving literacy, spreading concerns, regulations, and cultural practices can elevate consumers towards healthy post-purchase behaviour.

GREEN MARKETING STRATEGIES

Understanding Consumer Barriers

- Identifying which customers are likely to want green products.
- Examining how different market segments make purchase decisions.
- Addressing all barriers before consumers change their behaviours.

Educating Consumers

- Businesses should act as educators, addressing environmental issues like pollution, climate change, and overfishing.
- Nonprofits and government agencies should also contribute to green education.

GREEN MARKETING STRATEGIES

Building Better Products

- Companies should create products that are equal to or better than conventional alternatives.
- Consumers value performance, reliability, and durability more than ecological soundness.

Being transparent

- Companies should inform the public about their true environmental impact and attempt to reduce it.
- Identifying and addressing historical concerns about their products or operations is crucial.

GREEN MARKETING STRATEGIES

Offering More

- Companies should ensure consumers understand the returns on their investment.
- Consumers are more willing to try new green products when they understand their environmental benefits.

Bringing Products to the People

- Companies must ensure consumers can find their products.
- Consumers are increasingly concerned about the environmental and social impacts of products they buy, but their intentions often fail to translate into action.

GREEN MARKETING STRATEGIES

- Green campaigns often encounter a lag between concept and practice due to consumers' insincerity, laziness, posturing, or other unsavoury traits.
- Furthermore, businesses have not sufficiently educated consumers about the benefits of green products nor created offerings that effectively meet their needs.
- Despite consumers' desire to act in environmentally friendly ways, they rely on businesses to lead the way.
- According to a global survey, 61% of consumers believe corporations should take the lead in tackling climate change.

GREEN MARKETING STRATEGIES

- Businesses need to develop more and better Earth-friendly products and educate the consumers.
- The 2007 National Technology Readiness Survey found that more than two-thirds of participants say they prefer to do business with environmentally responsible companies, but almost half say it is difficult to find green goods and services.
- Corporations can reap multiple benefits by going green, such as reducing energy consumption, lessening risks, meeting competitive threats, enhancing their brands, and increasing revenues.

ROLE OF GREEN CONSUMERS

- Consumer behaviour is influenced by two main components: the individual as well as the institutional environment.
- The concept of green consumer behaviour has emerged as a social trend and has gained importance over time.
- There are several key factors that play a significant role in shaping green consumer behaviour.

ROLE OF GREEN CONSUMERS

1. Cultural and religious influences

- Cultural and religious beliefs impact consumer attitudes towards environmental stewardship and the use of eco-friendly products and technologies.
- Studies have shown that a person's cultural and religious affiliations can shape their behaviour as a green consumer.
- E.g. Buddhism teaches principles of sustainability, with the Dalai Lama advocating for climate action, reforestation, and ecosystem preservation.

ROLE OF GREEN CONSUMERS

2. Age, gender and income

- They have a significant impact on green consumer behaviour.
- Young consumers are more open to adopting new technologies and trends.
- Conversely, older consumers tend to be more conservative with their spending habits.
- The role of gender in green consumer behaviour is less understood, but some studies suggest that women are more environmentally conscious than men.

ROLE OF GREEN CONSUMERS

3. Psychographic factors: personality traits, lifestyle, social class, habits, behaviours, and interests, also influence consumer behaviour.

4. Environmental attitudes: Individuals with a strong environmental concern are more likely to make choices that support a healthy environment, such as recycling and conserving resources like water, gasoline, and electricity.

IMPACT OF GREEN CONSUMERISM

- Positive green consumer behaviour can be influenced by the environment one is in.
- This behaviour is shaped by how consumers perceive products, practices, and companies.
- These perceptions can be influenced through various forms of media such as news, newspapers, television, and movies.
- By showcasing and educating people about green products, media can help break misconceptions.
- Apart from product knowledge, people also base their purchasing decisions on various other factors.

IMPACT OF GREEN CONSUMERISM

The essence of green consumerism lies in a comprehensive and mindful approach to resource management that addresses, foresees, fulfils, and safeguards the needs of all stakeholders while preserving the natural environment and human health.

Green Consumerism is essential for several reasons:

- Promotes minimal packaging and encourages the reuse of materials like paper and plastic bags.
- Enhances energy efficiency, leading to cost savings, reduced utility bills, and decreased greenhouse gas emissions.
- Lowers emissions from transportation and industrial activities, contributing to cleaner air and reduced pollution levels.

IMPACT OF GREEN CONSUMERISM

- Stricter emissions standards enforced due to advocacy and programs promoting green consumerism.
- Reduced emissions from engines and motors, adoption of cleaner fuel options.
- Demand for organic and locally sourced food due to healthier options without artificial fertilizers, hormones, antibiotics, or pesticides.
- Recognising the impact of depleting green cover on natural habitats and making sustainable choices for long-term planet health.

GREEN CONSUMERSHIP STRATEGIES

- **Save Energy:** Mindfully reduce energy consumption by turning off lights and electronics when not in use.
- **Change Your Mindset:** Consume products and services that reduce natural resource depletion, habitat loss, and environmental degradation.
- **Use Solar and Renewable Energy:** Consider using solar products that harness the sun's energy instead of relying solely on electricity.
- **Collaborate** with governments, energy production facilities, industries, manufacturers, and consumers in investing in renewable energy solutions.

GREEN CONSUMERSHIP STRATEGIES

- **Check Energy Labels:** Avoid energy-intensive products and opt for products with lower energy consumption.
- **Prioritise Green Energy:** Prefer clean and renewable energy whenever possible.
- **Recycling:** Choose eco-friendly alternatives and recyclable products.
- **Purchase Locally Grown and Organic Foods:** Reduce carbon emissions associated with transportation and minimise the harmful effects of artificial pesticides and fertilizers.

GREEN CONSUMERSHIP STRATEGIES

- **Transparency:** Companies should be transparent about their practices, including sourcing and production processes.
- **Authenticity:** Companies should demonstrate a genuine commitment to sustainability by offering green products and services.
- **Emphasizing Pro-Environmental Solutions and Benefits:** Companies should highlight the environmental advantages of their products.
- **Creating Long-Lasting Products:** Companies should prioritise extending the life cycle of their products.

GREEN CONSUMERSHIP STRATEGIES

- **Utilizing Cause Marketing and Environmental Certifications:** Cause marketing involves directing a portion of product profits towards non-profit causes.
- **Eco-labels:** Eco-labels like Energy Star, USDA's Certified Organic, and the recycling logo significantly impact consumer purchasing decisions.
- **Environmental Product Declarations:** They provide detailed information about a product's life cycle's environmental impact.

GREEN CONSUMPTION EXAMPLES

- Seafood consumers favour products with Marine Stewardship Council's logo, indicating responsible environmental harvesting.
- Coffee drinkers in Canada and the US seek organic beans with certifications like the Bird-Friendly seal.
- Mexico's Forest Stewardship Council has certified over 25 million hectares of forest gardens in 54 countries, doubling coverage since 1998.
- The European Blue Flag campaign in 20 European countries has identified over 2,750 marinas and beaches as environmentally friendly.
- Thai consumers have increased usage of energy-efficient single-door refrigerators.

GREEN CONSUMPTION EXAMPLES

- Global consumers are reducing the need for medium coal-fired power plants by switching to energy-saving compact fluorescent lamps.
- Governments, organisations, and homeowners are installing solar or wind turbines instead of relying solely on the main power grid.

04

CASE STUDIES

01

Case study 1: A case study from Vietnam

02

Case study 2: A case study from Qingdao, China.

03

Case study 3: Influencing Factors for Sustainable Dietary Transformation—A Case Study of German Food Consumption.

CASE STUDY 1

Determinants of green consumer behavior: A case study from Vietnam

This study uses a survey to investigate factors affecting green consumption behaviour. The demographic data shows both males and females are interested in green consumption habits, with the majority being young, educated individuals.

Previous research on green consumption has identified environmental knowledge and attitude factors as key factors. It emphasises the importance of customers' attitudes towards green consumption, their concerns about environmental issues, and their impact on others.

Businesses should incorporate these factors into their long-term strategic planning to increase green purchasing. To draw customers' attention to green products, businesses can use promotion methods, provide hands-on learning opportunities, and foster a positive perception of their usefulness.

The study investigates the factors influencing green consumption behaviour, focusing on attitudes, societal norms, and environmental concerns. It found that consumers with a positive attitude towards green products are more likely to purchase them. Environmental concerns are also crucial, with consumers who are more concerned about the environment and have relevant knowledge being more likely to purchase green products.

Awareness of green consumption behaviour has no significant impact on it, but indirectly affects other factors. Consumers perceive that using green products will help protect the environment and have a positive attitude when buying, consuming, and promoting green products. The research is significant for understanding customers' green consumption habits and guiding businesses in capturing and tapping into people's psychology to build marketing and advertising strategies.

CASE STUDY 2

What affects green consumer behaviour in China? A case study from Qingdao.

The study explores green consumer behavior in China, examining personal influence, knowledge of green consumption, attitudes, internal and external moderators, and behavior. The rapid urbanisation and industrialisation in China could significantly influence consumers' attitudes and behaviour.

The study investigates green consumption in China, incorporating internal and external moderators to understand the factors influencing it. It focuses on three aspects: purchasing, using, and recycling. The approach is novel, providing more precise results and recommending policy options for the Chinese government.

Attitudes are the most significant predictor of purchasing behavior, while income, perceived consumer effectiveness, and age determine usage behavior. Recycling behaviour is strongly influenced by using behaviour. Environmental technologies, economic policies, and social initiatives are crucial for economic sustainability, but their impact depends on changing consumption patterns and behavior.

Green consumption is a key element in academic and policy debates, with factors such as demographics, environmental knowledge, attitudes, values, and internal and external moderators influencing it. However, approaches like the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) have limitations, such as the complexity of integrated models and the lack of correlation between value variables and household electricity conservation.

CASE STUDY 3

Influencing Factors for Sustainable Dietary Transformation—A Case Study of German Food Consumption.

A case study in Germany compared food consumption with sustainability pillars and dietary recommendations. The study found that purchasing decisions are largely influenced by health-related factors and few consumers align their diets with low environmental impact. A large portion of consumers opt for cheap foods, regardless of health and environmental consequences. Price is the main factor in food choices from a sustainability standpoint. Policymakers should financially incentivise consumers for healthy and environmentally friendly diets to prevent unhealthy consumption. Economic factors also influence food choices, with higher costs of plant-based and organic products leading to unhealthy habits.

This study also explores the factors influencing German consumers' dietary choices, revealing the gap between sustainable dietary patterns and actual consumption habits. It highlights the current food market's limitations and suggests that more educational campaigns could help promote healthier eating habits. Nutrition education could be a valuable tool for developing effective educational strategies.

German consumers are increasingly adopting environmentally conscious diets, but there is a gap between their commitment to sustainable products and actual consumption. Research is needed to understand consumer motivation and willingness to change. Cost of groceries can influence dietary decisions, with low prices of unsustainable options leading to high consumption. However, a nutritionally adequate diet can be purchased for lower expenses. Policymakers should encourage healthier, environmentally sensible dietary patterns with economic incentives and focus on best practices for transforming dietary trends towards health and ecological sustainability.

04

ASSESSMENT

Q1

What is green consumption primarily focused on?

- A. Personal gain
- B. Environmental impact
- C. Social status
- D. Economic benefits

Q2

What are green products known for?

- A. Using non-recyclable materials
- B. Increasing waste and energy usage
- C. Reducing packaging
- D. Containing toxic ingredients

Q3

What has been a significant driver behind the rise in green consumer behaviour over the past decade?

- A. Government regulations
- B. Personal preferences
- C. Commitments to cut energy usage
- D. Lack of awareness about eco-friendly products

Q4

How can companies demonstrate a genuine commitment to sustainability?

- A. Increase plastic packaging
- B. Use non-recyclable materials
- C. Offer green products and services
- D. Avoid transparency

Q5

What plays a crucial role in consumer behaviour according to the provided information?

- A. Social media influencers
- B. Environmental attitudes
- C. Celebrity endorsements
- D. Fashion trends

Q6

What is one of the strategies mentioned to promote green consumership?

- A. Increase energy consumption
- B. Use non-renewable energy sources
- C. Purchase locally grown and organic foods
- D. Ignore energy labels

Answer Key

Q1: B

Q2: C

Q3: C

Q4: C

Q5: B

Q6: C

04

**KEY TERMS AND
DEFINITIONS**

- Green consumption behaviour - using sustainable, eco-friendly products.
- Green products - environment friendly products that use recyclable materials.
- Green consumerism -customers using environmentally friendly products but with
- different focuses and meanings.
- Green marketing - a business practice that promotes products and services based on environmental initiatives.
- Green marketing practices.
- Sustainable marketing - a strategic move to connect with conscious consumers.

04

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Thank You
Any questions?

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